

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part XIII : Binding of Metal Cations to Casein Sols on the Addition of Electrolytes

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The binding of a few transition metal cations by α -, β - and unfractionated casein sols, stabilised at pH 7, has been studied. The value for a given ion increases with increase in concentration of the ion in solution and attains, ultimately, a final maximum value which varies with the nature of ion. The intrinsic binding constant, the equilibrium constant, standard free energy change and standard entropy change for the first metal ion complexed have been calculated.

PROTEINS, in general, have a tendency to bind, i. e., to complex with, transition metal cations. This tendency has been investigated by different workers in the case of a number of proteins by employing equilibrium dialysis¹⁻⁴, potentiometric⁵⁻⁷ and other techniques⁸⁻¹⁰. The maximum number of cations bound by the various proteins, however, has not been reported in most cases and the work on casein and its fractions has not received adequate attention. The present paper describes complex formation of casein sols, stabilised at pH 7 with Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Ag^+ ions by employing the equilibrium dialysis technique.

Experimental

Casein and its major fractions, α - and β -caseins, were isolated from bovine skim milk by the methods described before¹¹. Sols. of one per cent concentration were prepared, in each case, at pH 7.0 by suspending required amounts in 20 ml of CO_2 free distilled water in 100 ml measuring flasks, adding enough of aqueous alkali (NaOH), gradually with constant stirring (magnetic), to dissolve the casein and to raise the pH of the system to about 8.0. The excess of the alkali was

removed by dialysis. The pH values were checked at different stages during dialysis and were adjusted finally at pH 7.0 (± 0.05).

The electrolytes used were the chlorides of zinc, cobalt, nickel and copper and nitrate of silver. All the electrolytes used were of A. R. (B. D. H.) quality and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

Several 5 ml portions of a casein sol, taken in cellophane bags, were placed in contact with aqueous solutions of increasing concentrations of an electrolyte. The amount of a cation taken up by the sol. on the attainment of equilibrium (which required usually 36 hrs) was estimated by noting the fall in concentration of the cation by the usual analytical methods. Solutions of various electrolytes were prepared in 0.15 M $NaNO_3$ to avoid Donnan Membrane effect.

Results and Discussion

The number of moles of various metal cations bound by casein sols, stabilised at pH 7.0, are plotted against logarithm of the concentrations of unbound (free) ions in equilibrium in Figures 1 to 5.

Fig. 1. Effect of concentration of free Zn^{2+} ions on their binding with caseins. [X—X, α -Casein, Δ — Δ , Whole Casein ; O—O, β -Casein]

Fig. 2. Effect of concentration of free Co^{2+} ions on their binding with caseins. [X—X, α -Casein ; Δ — Δ , Whole Casein ; O—O, β -Casein]

Fig. 3. Effect of concentration of free Ni^{2+} ions on their binding with caseins. [X—X, α -Casein; Δ — Δ , Whole Casein; \circ — \circ , β -Casein]

Fig. 4. Effect of concentration of free Cu^{2+} ions on their binding with caseins. [X—X, α -Casein; Δ — Δ , Whole Casein; \circ — \circ , β -Casein]

Fig. 5. Effect of concentration of free Ag^+ ions on their binding with caseins. [X—X, α -Casein; Δ — Δ , Whole Casein; \circ — \circ , β -Casein]

It is seen that the number of moles (r) of any of the ions bound by casein or its major fractions increases with increase in the concentration of free ions in solution at equilibrium and, ultimately, tends to attain a final maximum value. The maximum values for various metal cations are given in Table I. The value for Ag^+ ion in each case is the highest, and that for Zn^{2+} is the lowest. The values for Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions are rather close to one another. The binding of each ion is maximum in the case of α -casein and minimum in the case of β -casein.

It has been shown earlier from studies based on heats of ionisation of various caseins reported in a

previous paper¹¹ that the functional groups which protonise at $\text{pH } 7.0$ are carboxyls, imidazoles and a part of the phosphoric acid groups. The numbers of these groups contained in the caseins under examination, as obtained from their titration curves¹¹, are included in Table I. Gurd and Goodman⁴, working with human serum albumin, have shown that at $\text{pH} \leq 7$, Zn^{2+} ions can be bound only to imidazole groups. Tanford⁹ as well as Fiess and Klotz^{1,2}, working with α -casein, β -casein, bovine serum albumin, β -lactoglobulin and lysozyme, have adduced spectroscopic evidence to show that Cu^{2+} ion can be bound to carboxyl as well as imidazole groups at about the same pH . Rao and Hira Lal¹⁰, using bovine serum albumin, have shown

TABLE 1—MAXIMUM BINDING OF Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} AND Ag^+ IONS TO SOLS. (1%) OF CASEIN AND ITS FRACTIONS STABILISED AT pH 7.0

Description of the sample	Max. binding (moles/10 ⁵ g Casein)					Number of various groups ionising at pH 7.0				
	Zn ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ag ⁺	Ist. eq. phosphate	Carboxyl	Imidazole	2nd eq. phosphate*	Total
Whole casein	23	76	73	80	153	29	94	18	8	149
α-casein	25	88	84	91	174	32	110	19	10	171
β-casein	22	69	64	70	138	23	87	20	5	135

*Note: The second equivalent of phosphoric acid gets completely ionised only at pH 8.4 (II). The number given in this column is the number of groups which ionise at pH 7.0.

similar behaviour of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions under similar conditions. Fiess³, who included casein also in his studies, has shown that phosphoserine groups are also involved in the binding process.

In the light of the previous work referred to above, the relatively lower value for the binding of zinc ions appears to be due to the presence of relatively smaller number of imidazole groups, with which alone it can interact. It is seen that roughly one Zn^{2+} ion is bound per imidazole group in each casein. The values for the binding of other cations are much higher. This appears to be due to their capacity to complex with carboxyl and phosphate groups, besides imidazole groups, as well. The values for Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions, being roughly half of the total number of groups ionising at the prevailing pH, it appears that roughly one metal ion is bound at two of the available sites. Each Ag^+ ion, carrying only half as much charge, appears to be bound at only one of the available sites, roughly speaking.

Fiess and Klotz², by applying the law of mass action, have shown that if all the binding sites have the same intrinsic binding constant, k , then

$$\lim_{[Free\ ion] \rightarrow 0} \frac{r}{[Free\ ion]} = nk \quad (i)$$

where r is the number of moles of the metal ion bound per 10⁵g protein and n is the number of available sites.

Fig. 6. Plots of $r/[Free\ ion]$ versus $[Free\ ion]$ for the binding of Co^{2+} ions to caseins. \times — \times , α-Casein; \triangle — \triangle , Whole Casein; \circ — \circ , β-Casein]

Further, for a single set of binding sites, $nk = k_1$, where k_1 is the equilibrium constant for the first metal ion complexed with the protein. Thus the intrinsic binding constant k and hence the equilibrium constant k_1 for the first metal ion complexed can be evaluated from a graph of $r/[Free\ ion]$ versus $[Free\ ion]$, and noting the intercept at $[Free\ ion]=0$. The plots of $r/[Free\ ion]$ against $[Free\ ion]$ for Co^{2+} ion in the case of α-, β-, and whole caseins are shown in Fig. 6. The curves for other ions were also drawn in a similar manner. The values of k_1 , as obtained by extrapolating the various graphs to zero concentration of free ions, are given in Table 2.

The intrinsic binding constant, k , for a single set of binding sites can also be calculated by the simplified form of Scatchard equation (12), viz.,

$$\ln \frac{r}{(n-r)[Free\ ion]} = \ln k \quad (ii)$$

which has been used by a number of investigators in the case of various proteins. The correction factor due to electrostatic interaction included in the complete equation, has been shown to be negligibly small and has been excluded by various workers^{2,13}. The data relating to the dependence of the extent of binding on the concentration of free metal ions, plotted in Figures 1 to 5, can, therefore, be used for calculating k and hence k_1 . The values of $\log k$ (Table 3) are seen to be fairly constant to justify the application of Scatchard equation to the binding of various ions to casein and its major fractions. It is also interesting to note that the values of k_1 , as obtained from equations (i) and (ii), are in good agreement with each other (Table 2).

Knowing the value of equilibrium constant, k_1 , the standard free energy decrease, $-\Delta F_1^0$, for the complexing of first metal ion can be computed from the well known thermodynamic relationship

$$-\Delta F_1^0 = RT \ln k_1 \quad (iii)$$

These values, given in Table 2, are of the same order as reported by Fiess and Klotz² for the binding of Cu^{2+} ions to a number of proteins. The values for binding of a given cation to various caseins decrease in the order

The binding of α-casein, therefore, appears to be the strongest.

The values for the binding of various cations to a given casein decrease in the order

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS (k_1), FREE ENERGIES ($-\Delta F^0_1$) AND ENTROPIES (ΔS^0_1) OF BINDING OF VARIOUS CATIONS TO CASEIN AND CASEIN FRACTIONS AT pH 7.0

Cation	k_1	$-\Delta F^0_1$ (Kcal/mole)	ΔS^0_1 (cal/mole/deg)
<i>Whole Casein</i>			
Zn ²⁺	6.61 × 10 ⁴ (6.39 × 10 ⁴)	6.714	22.1
Co ²⁺	1.70 × 10 ⁴ (1.65 × 10 ⁴)	5.900	19.4
Ni ²⁺	1.05 × 10 ⁴ (0.99 × 10 ⁴)	5.603	18.4
Cu ²⁺	2.33 × 10 ⁴ (2.21 × 10 ⁴)	6.089	20.1
Ag ⁺	4.15 × 10 ⁴ (3.78 × 10 ⁴)	6.437	21.2
<i>α-Casein</i>			
Zn ²⁺	6.70 × 10 ⁴ (6.07 × 10 ⁴)	6.730	22.4
Co ²⁺	2.12 × 10 ⁴ (1.73 × 10 ⁴)	6.031	19.9
Ni ²⁺	1.32 × 10 ⁴ (1.19 × 10 ⁴)	5.741	18.9
Cu ²⁺	2.72 × 10 ⁴ (2.41 × 10 ⁴)	6.182	20.4
Ag ⁺	4.78 × 10 ⁴ (4.43 × 10 ⁴)	6.523	21.5
<i>β-Casein</i>			
Zn ²⁺	4.0 × 10 ⁴ (4.21 × 10 ⁴)	6.415	21.1
Co ²⁺	0.87 × 10 ⁴ (0.67 × 10 ⁴)	5.493	18.1
Ni ²⁺	0.65 × 10 ⁴ (0.51 × 10 ⁴)	5.313	17.5
Cu ²⁺	1.01 × 10 ⁴ (1.21 × 10 ⁴)	5.581	18.4
Ag ⁺	2.41 × 10 ⁴ (2.26 × 10 ⁴)	6.070	20.0

Note : The values of k_1 , given in the parentheses, are calculated from Scatchard equation.

TABLE 3—LOG K VALUES FOR THE BINDING OF VARIOUS CATIONS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS WITH CASEIN AND CASEIN FRACTIONS

Description of the sample	Concentration (moles/litre)		Concentration (moles/litre)	log k			
	Zn ²⁺	log k		Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ag ⁺
<i>Whole Casein</i>	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.634	16 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.045	1.819	2.160	2.371
	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.694	25 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.010	1.813	2.141	2.375
	4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.665	40 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.012	1.798	2.098	2.321
<i>α-Casein</i>	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.487	16 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.010	1.866	2.149	2.477
	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.619	25 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.922	1.844	2.155	2.401
	4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.538	40 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.010	1.845	2.143	2.365
<i>β-Casein</i>	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.463	16 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.744	1.544	1.967	2.287
	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.499	25 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.670	1.505	1.968	2.204
	4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.518	40 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.668	1.579	1.932	2.177

The standard entropy change, ΔS^0_1 , for the complexing of the first metal cation, can be calculated by the well known expression,

$$\Delta F^0_1 = \Delta H^0_1 - T\Delta S^0_1 \quad (iv)$$

Since in the case of interaction of proteins with the various ions included in the present investigations, the standard enthalpy change, ΔH^0_1 , has been found to be negligibly small (2), the above equation may be put as

$$\Delta S^0_1 \approx \frac{-\Delta F^0_1}{T} \quad (v)$$

The values of ΔS^0_1 calculated from equation (v) at the temperature of the experiment, viz., 30°, are included in Table 2.

The binding of various cations to caseins is seen to be accompanied by increase of entropy. This may be due to the fact that the interacting casein particles as well as the ions are largely hydrated, there being several polarised molecules attached to them. Some, if not all, of these molecules are released, during the complexing reaction which, therefore, results in an increase in the number of molecular species and hence in entropy of the system.

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